

Proton Magnetic Relaxation Study of I^- and Rb^+ in Aqueous Solutions

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Using the isotropic dilution technique, the proton relaxation rate in aqueous solution of KI and RbI has been measured to evaluate intermolecular proton relaxation rate caused by ion-proton magnetic dipole-dipole interaction. The dependence of the correlation time and the proton-ion distance on the salt concentration has been examined and discussed.

Nuclear magnetic relaxation measurements yield information about the structure of hydration spheres around ions in aqueous electrolyte solutions. The distance between the ion-nucleus and the water-protons in the first hydration sphere can be determined from the intermolecular proton-ion nuclear magnetic dipole-dipole contribution to the proton magnetic relaxation rate^{1,2}. The structure of the first hydration sphere was previously determined by computational methods³. Further studies were carried out by using a combined neutron and X-ray scattering methods by Narten *et al.*⁴ and recently by others⁵.

In the present work, the proton-iodide and the proton-rubidium relaxation rates were measured at various concentrations of KI and RbI in order to investigate, in which way the correlation time τ_c^{**} and the proton-ion distance depend on the salt concentration.

Results and Discussion

Analysis of relaxation data: The proton magnetic relaxation rate of an aqueous salt solution consists of the proton-proton contribution $(1/T)_{pp}$ caused by magnetic dipole-dipole interaction between the water protons, the proton-cation $(1/T)_{pI}$, and the proton-anion $(1/T)_{pI}$ relaxation contributions¹,

$$1/T_1 = (1/T_1)_{pp} + (1/T_1)_{pI} + (1/T_1)_{pI} \quad (1)$$

In order to separate the two proton-ion contributions, it is advantageous to use a salt for which one ion has a negligibly small magnetic moment. Therefore for the study of I^- , the cation used was K^+ .

Because of the magnitude of the gyromagnetic ratio of the protons, the proton-proton contribution is much larger than the proton-ion contribution. To overcome this experimental problem, the protons of the electrolyte solution were partially replaced by deuterons. The experiments were carried out as follows. The proton relaxation rates of the solutions of the investigated salt in mixture of normal and heavy water with varying proton contents but

constant salt concentration, were measured and the results extrapolated to zero proton mole fraction. Figs. 1 and 2 represent these measurements for KI and RbI respectively. These values are the average of three to ten single readings. The obtained values of proton relaxation rate $1/T_1$ in pure water are in agreement with the values obtained previously^{1,2}. The deviation was less than 3%. The results also reveal a concentration dependence of the relaxation rate of both KI and RbI, as $1/T_1$ decreases with the concentration of salt. This behaviour was denoted^{1,2} for structure-breaking salts in contrary to structure-forming salts such as BaI_2 and MgI_2 . In addition, this dependence diminishes with increasing D_2O in the water mixture due to the same reason.

Fig. 1. Proton relaxation rates in KI/ H_2O/D_2O system at different H_2O mole fraction as a function of molal salt concentration \bar{m} : (Δ) 1.0, (\blacktriangle) 0.5, (\square) 0.2 and (\blacksquare) 0.1.

Fig. 2. Proton relaxation rates in RbI/H₂O/D₂O system at different H₂O mole fraction as a function of molal salt concentration \bar{m} : (Δ) 1.0, (∇) 0.7, (\square) 0.4, (\blacksquare) 0.2 and (\circ) 0.1.

According to a relation⁶ connecting the proton relaxation rate $1/T_1$ and the proton mole fraction X_{H_2O} , plots of $(1/T_1) \cdot 1/\eta_r$ vs X_{H_2O} for each salt were constructed (η_r is the relative viscosity of H₂O and D₂O at each mole fraction). A straight line was obtained with an intercept at $X_{H_2O} = 0$, corresponding to $(1/T_1(0))$, where

$$(1/T_1(0)) = (1/T)_{pI, D_2O}$$

The extrapolated relaxation rates $(1/T(0))$ for various salt concentrations are given in Table 1. The published value for 6 \bar{m} KI solution⁷ agrees fairly well with that obtained in this work.

The intermolecular proton-ion relaxation rate is found to consist of two parts¹, the relaxation rate caused by the ions belonging to the first hydration sphere $(1/T_1)_{pI}^I$ and the relaxation rate due to the ions not belonging to the first coordination sphere of a water molecule $(1/T_1)_{pI}^{II}$

$$(1/T_1)_{pI} = (1/T_1)_{pI}^I + (1/T_1)_{pI}^{II} \quad (2)$$

$(1/T_1)_{pI}^{II}$ is proportional to the number density C_I' of the ions (the iodide ion concentration given as number of ions per cm³) according to the relation⁶,

$$(1/T_1)_{pI}^{II} = \frac{16 \pi \gamma_I^2 \gamma_S^2 \hbar^2 S(S+1) C_I'}{27 b D} \quad (3)$$

where, b is the closest distance of approach outside the first hydration sphere between two nonequal nuclei of spins I and S and different gyromagnetic ratios γ_I^2 and γ_S^2 , \hbar the Plank constant and \bar{D} the mean self-diffusion coefficient for the interacting molecules (D₂O and I⁻ ion). The constants $[\gamma_I^2 \gamma_S^2 \hbar^2 S(S+1)]$ for I⁻ and Rb⁺ have values of 2.0172 and 0.96×10^{-37} cm⁶ s⁻² respectively. The closest proton-ion distance of approach outside the first hydration sphere b has been estimated for KI and RbI by geometrical consideration as described previously⁷. The b values of H—I and H—Rb were found to be 4.20 and 3.84 Å respectively, and agree well with the distances obtained by Lawrence and Kruh⁸. The values of \bar{D} were calculated by using the previously given data for KI and RbI^{9,10}.

The values of relaxation rate $(1/T_1)_{pI, D_2O}^{II}$ in equation (3) due to the bulk solution are calculated for iodide and rubidium ions and listed in Table 1. In order to obtain the relaxation rate of a H₂O-solution, the relaxation rate has to be divided by μ_r , the relative microviscosity in the first hydration sphere. Estimation of μ_r for various concentrations of salts was done as given earlier⁷.

TABLE I—CONCENTRATION DEPENDENCE OF PROTON-ION RELAXATION CONTRIBUTION AND PROTON-ION DISTANCE

Salt	$\frac{C^*_{I'}}{m}$	$\left(\frac{1}{T_1}\right)_0$ s ⁻¹	$\left(\frac{1000}{T_1}\right)_{pI}^{I+II}$, D ₂ O s ⁻¹	$\left(\frac{1000}{T_1}\right)_{pI}^{II}$, D ₂ O s ⁻¹	$\left(\frac{1000}{T_1}\right)_{pI}^I$, D ₂ O s ⁻¹	a Å	b Å	
KI	0.40	0.011 7	—	0.12	—	—	—	
	1.19	0.011 7	—	0.32	—	—	—	
	2.07	0.012 8	1.55	0.53	1.02	2.81	2.88	
	2.50	0.013 3	1.86	0.63	1.23	2.76	3.07	
	3.11	0.013 3	2.53	0.76	1.77	2.73	3.00	
	4.08	0.013 6	3.56	0.99	2.57	2.73	2.96	
	4.57	0.013 6	3.65	1.09	2.56	2.73	3.04	
	5.49	0.014 0	4.75	1.29	3.46	2.76	2.96	
	6.08	0.014 3	4.85	1.42	3.43	2.77	3.04	
RbI	$\frac{C^*_{I'}}{m}$	$\left(\frac{1}{T_1}\right)_0$ s ⁻¹	$\left(\frac{1000}{T_1}\right)_{p-RbI}^{I+II}$, D ₂ O s ⁻¹	$\left(\frac{1000}{S_1}\right)_{p-RbI}^{II}$, D ₂ O s ⁻¹	$\left(\frac{1000}{T_1}\right)_{p-RbI}^I$, D ₂ O s ⁻¹	$\left(\frac{1000}{T_1}\right)_{p-Rb^+}^I$, D ₂ O s ⁻¹	a Å	b Å
	2.5	0.014 6	3.30	0.254	3.05	1.84	1.81	2.39
	3.5	0.016 0	5.74	0.335	5.40	2.89	1.78	2.34
	4.5	0.018 0	8.20	0.409	7.80	5.28	1.73	2.12
	5.5	0.018 7	9.70	0.472	9.23	5.86	1.85	2.24

Fig. 3 represents the values of $(1/T_1)_{PI, H_2O}$ for iodide and rubidium ions at different salt concentrations. The resulting curves show increase of the first coordination sphere proton-ion relaxation contribution with rate in water with salt concentration.

Fig. 3. First coordination sphere proton-ion relaxation contribution in H_2O as a function of molal salt concentration \bar{m} : (Δ) I and (\square) Rb.

Considering now the relaxation rate caused by the first coordination sphere⁶,

$$(1/T_1)_{PI}^I = \frac{4}{3} \gamma_I^2 \gamma_H^2 \hbar^2 S(S+1) \frac{\hat{n} C_I^*}{55.5} \tau_o^{**} \frac{g(a,b,m,q)}{a^6} \quad (4)$$

where, \hat{n} is the first coordination number of a water molecule with respect to the ions¹¹, which is taken from X-ray scattering data⁴ to be 6 for each of Rb^+ and I^- ; C_I^* the salt concentration on the aquamolality scale (mole salt per 55.5 mole water); τ_o^{**} the translational correlation time for the proton-ion vector inside the first hydration sphere, whose value was estimated from the diffusion coefficient⁶ and was found to be 2 and 9 ps for H-I and H-Rb respectively, and these values are correct compared to the published ones⁷; a the closest protonion distance of approach inside the first hydration sphere; the term $g(a,b,m,q)$ is given as⁷

$$g(a,b,m,q) = a^6 (r_o^{-6}) \quad (5)$$

in which m and q are two numbers describing geometrical details of the ion-proton pair distribution function and r_o is the vector connecting the proton spin and the electron spin of the ion; the values of

$g(a,b,m,q)$ are found to be 4.54 and 4.63×10^{44} for KI and RbI respectively⁷. Inserting the values of \hat{n} , C_I^* , τ_o^{**} and $g(a,b,m,q)$ in equation (4), the distance (a) was estimated for I^- and Rb^+ at different salt concentrations. In addition, the closest proton-ion distance of approach outside the first hydration sphere (b) was recalculated according to equation (4). Both the values of a and b are given in Table 1.

The variation of $(1/C_I^*) (1/T_1)_{PI, D_2O}$ with varying molal salt concentration (C_m^*) is plotted (Fig. 4), where C_I^* is the number densities of the ion. The slopes of the resulting linear curves agree with that of NaCl proton rate and are opposite to that of LiCl given by Langer and Hertz⁷. This would be referred to the nature of NaCl, KI and RbI as structure-breaking salts, whereas LiCl is a structure-forming one. LiCl tends to more hydration with the water molecules and affects strongly the correlation times τ_o^{**} compared to I^- and Rb^+ .

Fig. 4. Concentration dependence of the proton-ion relaxation contribution: (Δ) H-I and (\square) H-Rb.

Because, $(1/C_D) (1/T_1)_{PI, D_2O}$ is proportional to τ_o^{**} and to (r_o^{-6}) as given in equations (4) and (5), the increase of $(1/C_I^*) (1/T_1)_{PI, D_2O}$ with increasing concentration could be attributed to an increase of τ_o^{**} and/or to a decrease of (r_o^{-6}) , the vector connecting the proton spin and the electron spin of the ion. However it is very unlikely that the correlation time τ_o^{**} increases with increasing concentration as it should be according to the behaviour of the self-diffusion coefficient. This would require a drastic decrease of (r_o^{-6}) . This conclusion is in agreement with the concentration-dependence of the proton-iodide and proton-rubidium distances outside the first hydration sphere, as shown in Fig. 5, whereas the distance of approach inside the

first hydration sphere of I⁻ and Rb⁺ ions might correspond to a fully symmetrical orientation of the water molecules, i.e. the electric dipole axis of water molecules predominantly points away from the cation towards the anion. This conclusion is in agreement with other structure-breaking ions⁷.

Fig. 5. Concentration dependence of the closest proton-ion distances of approach inside, (∇ , \blacksquare) a and outside, b (Δ , \square) the first hydration sphere: (Δ , \blacktriangle) H-I and (\square , \blacksquare) H-Rb.

Experimental

All chemicals were of E. Merck. The heavy water contained at least 99.9% D₂O (Merck uvasol). All salts were of 'suprapur grade'.

The samples of salts were prepared in heavy and normal water. In order to allow a comparison of the solutions in H₂O and D₂O, the concentration used was aquamolality \bar{m} (mole salt per 55.5 mole water), which for the H₂O-solution corresponds to the usual molality scale. Various concentrations of 0.400–6.078 \bar{m} and 2.5–5.5 \bar{m} were prepared for KI and Rb⁺ solutions respectively. From

each salt concentration, four or five solutions of different water mole fraction (X_{H_2O}) were prepared. The samples were contained in glass tubes with a filling height of 15 mm. The samples were freed from oxygen by the usual freeze-pump-thaw method.

All measurements were performed with a 90°– τ -90° pulse sequence technique using a pulse spectrophotometer¹. The resonance frequency was 25.57 MHz. The temperature was controlled in all the experiments to $25 \pm 0.3^\circ$ by pumping thermostated water-methanol mixture through the probe head.

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